

Impact of Innovation in Services Organization (marketing agencies)

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Abstract

The purpose of this article is to discover how the innovation in services area impact on an organization. Organizational lifestyles depends upon business profitability greater the business is worthwhile greater its existence will increase. At the same time as business profitability depends upon consumer pleasure in each form of an employer whether the business is production, buying and selling, or offerings offering. Whether or not it's miles small or big, so for the pleasure of current customer and enchantment of recent consumer your services ought to be sturdy. Innovation is one in every of five drivers of productiveness among skills, investment, corporation, and completion (Pryce, June 2007) that is the precise feature of entrepreneurship whether or not in an current business, public service institution or sole proprietorship. It is the method wherein entrepreneur creates new matters or make dependable changing's in present phenomena. There is a great deal confusion about the right definition of entrepreneurship and innovation. Some humans refers this time period to small commercial enterprise, others refer it to all new companies. In practice, however, many well-installed organizations have interaction in exceptionally successful entrepreneurship. The term, then, prefers not to an organization's length or age however to a certain kind of activity. at the coronary heart of that activity is innovation the effort to create reason-complete, targeted alternate in an business enterprise's financial or social potential (Drucker, 1998)

Introduction

Innovation is not only a new thing it is tendency to think about new and better ways of doing things and make them able for practical use. Innovation and advancement make things easier like in agriculture and industries it make world as a global village. Awareness of the importance of service innovation for the economic growth is a recent admiration. In past, people think that services are as non-innovative activities. The innovation literature was focused on the production sector, technological product development, and process innovation, and thus, innovation in services was addressed from a manufacturing viewpoint.

Gallouj examine the corresponding literature “assimilated services within the consolidated framework used for business segments and industrial products” (Gallouj, 2009). The danger of such a unfairness towards industrial is the irony of innovation in services and its effects, because innovation in services includes intangible or hidden innovations that are not confined by the traditional indicators of innovation in the manufacturing sector. However, the traditional approach has been gradually more challenged, mainly because the ignorance of the dynamics of the service sector was seen as inconsistent with the rise of the service economy, which now accounts for nearly 70% of gross domestic product and employment in member countries of the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2005).

According to the discussion about innovation in services should be increased beyond the traditional (technological) standpoint. A number of studies have thrown light on the specificities of innovation in services instead of traditional inclined point of view, which forced it to the adoption and use of technology (1997, Sundbo & Gallouj, & Tether). These studies take into account the main characteristics of the service creation – its intangibility, its equal and reciprocal relationship, and its locality – which makes it efficient to define innovation in services. The objective of this article is to review the existing literature on service innovation in order to recognize and evaluate distinguish models of the innovation process in services. The article also aims to show how the unresolved issues relative to the definition of service output have thrown in to the underestimation of the performance of service innovation in terms of productivity and employment.

Literature Review

Savona suggested that the characteristics of services have mostly been ignored by the innovation literature. There is a particular diagnostic problem of the definition of service output, which replicates on the definition of service innovation. When investigating service innovation, scholars have simply logical tools

planned for manufacturing within the traditional technical understanding of innovation. This tactic has directed to the misinterpretation and the irony of novelty in activities in services. (savona, 2009) argue that it has also directed to incorrect assumption that innovation in services has a comparatively insignificant effect on economic performance in relations of output and value added, associated to innovation in manufacturing. Therefore, a clear explanation of services and their features is a significant factor for the precise measuring of novelty output in services and the valuation of the actual economic outcome of services.

Nevertheless, “the study of services innovation points the inquiry of how a ‘service’ should be different” (DTI, 2007). Service creation is an accomplishment, or a handling procedure, that leads to a change of state, not the formation of a tangible good (Gallouj, 1998). Because of its undistinguishable nature or intangibility, its heterogeneity and wobbly character, service is hard to explain, and consequently it is also hard to measure its production and productivity (Melvien, 1995). Arriving at a definition of a service is convenient before discussing the problem of defining innovation in the service sector and gauging the productivity impression of innovation on services. However, there is no treaty today between economists about the hypothetical classification of service actions and their output (Gaudery, 2000). Therefore, this section of the study sets out to discuss, from a serious viewpoint, the most projecting arguments about the differences between goods and services, with a emphasis on the definition of services.

Occurrence of innovation

The occurrence of innovation depends on two factors internally and externally or within the company and outside the company .within the company sources is unexpected occurrences, incongruities, process needs, industry and market changes. And outside the company sources demographic changes, changes in perception, new knowledge. (Drucker, 1998)

Services Innovation and Economic Performance:

In this article Luisa Ferreira described the relationship between innovation and economic performance, in the services sector, using new data on innovation in service industries. Instead of establishing a simple direct link between innovation and labor productivity, they have taken into account not only the result of the innovation process but also the activities earlier to the market introduction of the innovation. Their work indicates that this maybe a relevant determinant of productivity.

The most relevant limitation of this investigation is its pure cross-section nature as innovation is naturally a dynamic process; the data set also enforced some significant limitations to the substitutions that could be used for innovation output and for productivity. Estimating the relationships as a system gives a negative impact of innovation output on productivity and a positive impact of intensity. This unexpected result leads to conclude that the econometric methods used are of vital importance in this background and that particular care must be taken in this respect in order to have confidence in the results one gets from the practical estimation of models.

This article is uncertain step to use more difficult quantitative methods and an exploratory work pointing to further investigation. The great sensitivity clearly indicates the need for further investigation in this area. It is still not clear actually which type of specification and estimation method should be preferred. The specific characteristics of the data require particular care with the econometric methods used

Another possible future improvement is to break the sample in two sub-samples, according to the intensity of the innovation behavior of the sector’s firms. Finally, it should be stressed that the data used comes from a survey that simply enlarges the scope of the universe under study to services industries, without taking into consideration the specific characteristics of innovative activities in these sectors (Weinstein, 1997). This is a difficult but very significant problem that needs to be addressed in the future. (Dodinho)

Impact of innovation

There are following sections which show the impact of innovation on economic performance, by comparing, on the one hand, the economic performances of innovating and non-innovating firms and, on the other hand, of firms or company spending on innovation above and below the sectorial averages. There are two

types of relationship between economic performance and innovation both from a conceptual and empirical point of view. More productivity creates more opportunities for innovation. Innovation has positive impact on economic performance which leads to customers satisfaction, productivity, profitability and loyalty (CAINELLI, EVANGELISTA, & SAVONA, 2003)

Conceptual Perspectives for Innovation in Service

The study of service innovation beyond the manufacturing based. They have wanted to speak that the activities in term of innovation will be habitually. In this view, the service-based approach and integrative approach are considered two important conceptualization frameworks that extend beyond the fixed viewpoint, which is represented by the assimilation approach. (Morrar, 2014)

Service innovation and economics performance

In service economy it not easy to identify and specify the whole innovation in the world we need to go beyond their performance in manufacturing as well as in service department depends an innovation; however the relationship between innovation and research in services & economic changes is classified. In service economy performance linked with research or innovation. Innovation in services and productivity (Gnllouj, 2009) relationship link between innovation in services & productivity is related to service specificities that effect the valuation of productivity.

Use of technical approach for valuation of innovation activities in services will lead to under estimate of both innovation & economic performance & it can create two types of gap or difference. (Gallouj D. &, 2010(a)) the innovation difference shows that our economies contain hidden innovation.

Production of new technologies (al, 1984 - 1987 - 1989)

By early studies 1980,s growth of service in fast economics shows that services were increase difficult to ignore very few innovation was set out by researchers to explore large past of economy. This phase of research require to study innovation in services using conceptual tools. As such this phase is seen as a attempt to subordinate services into vast senesce of innovation important attempt to assimilate services into innovation was (soetes, 2001) innovation in services follow different pattern a theory of research in services was proposed by (Barras, 1986) U.K innovation survey of 2005 shoes that mostly firms use few information source for innovation.

Management of innovation in services:

In 1993 innovation in services firm was taken under investigation (al G. e., 1993 - 1994) It is concluded that innovation is taken place in all sectors like banking insurance etc. In management consulting the innovation process is among the professionals. Gardreyetal. Identify the close relation to customers particularly service firms (czepiel, 1985) this is a benefit of service firm that manufacturing firm can learn from. However service firms are not quick innovation process.

Combinative effect of innovation

This study initiated with the idea that organizations interact with the environment and bring adoptable changes in response to environmental demands and opportunities under the guidance of their leaders, and offered two major withdrawals from the existing literature. First, that the combined adoption of innovation types over time helps developing organizational capabilities and affects organizational conduct and outcome. Opposing to previous research that mainly theorized and examined differences in the backgrounds of innovation types, they focused on the significances of innovation types and innovative that certain structures of innovation types over time will lead to unique competencies that positively affect organizational performance.

Second, that organizational succession service organizations does not follow a technological course and depends on the adoption of both technological and non-technological innovations. Opposing to past research that relied on the models of evolution of both technology based product and process innovations at the product

class level to explain consequences of innovation adoption in organizations, they advanced that co-adoption of different innovation types can better explain performance consequences of innovation in service organizations.

Theories of innovation

General Theory of Innovation by Greg Yezersky:

General Theory of Innovation was created by (Yezersky, 2002). The purpose of work was creating a theory related to understand the causes of and assisting mechanisms for development, success survival, and departure of the man-made systems started in 1988. The name of General Theory of Innovation was recommended by Dr. Noel Leon Rovira (Instituto Tecnológico y de Estudios Superiores de Monterrey, ITESM, Monterrey, Mexico) and adopted in 2005.

GTI is based on these facts and principles.

1. All the synthetic systems (such as products, processes, services, organizations, etc., regardless of their complexity and specific nature, change over time.
2. Regardless of its uncertainty, the process of evolution has a logic and prime direction.
3. Deviation from this evolutionary logic prearranges troubles for an upcoming innovation.
4. Instead, following the logic of the evolutionary process (intentionally or not) enables reversal of the odds and creation of successful innovations virtually on demand!
5. Knowledge of the evolutionary logic enables effective and efficient problem solving, reliable prediction of future evolutionary changes, objective judgment of the proposed innovations, and other essential for every business success functions.
6. Emergence of the science of innovation enables drastic risk and cost reduction while greatly improving the outcome.
7. Last but not least, any scientific theory can be effectively taught and learned, which enables creation of corporate “On-Demand Innovation” capability.

All these GTI capabilities were used to create various business applications, which were carefully tested to address the needs of real projects. They have proven their effectiveness beyond any doubt. A list of clients that benefited from application of GTI includes many prominent companies and institutions from all around the world. GTI has been also taught globally. General Theory of Innovation (GTI) is the only scientific theory of innovation with prescriptive and predictive capabilities and with the broadest range of applications.

Diffusion of Innovation Theory:

Diffusion research examines how ideas are spread among groups of people. Diffusion goes beyond the two-step flow theory, focusing on the conditions that increase or decrease the probability that an innovation, a new idea, product or practice, will be adopted by members of a given culture. In multi-step diffusion, the opinion leader still applies a large influence on the behavior of persons, called adopters, but there are also other arbitrators between the media and the audience's decision-making. One arbitrator is the change agent, someone who encourages an opinion leader to adopt or reject an innovation (infante, 1997).

Innovations are not adopted by all individuals in a social system at the same time. Instead, they tend to adopt in a time series, and can be classified into adopter categories based upon how long it takes for them to begin using the new idea. Practically speaking, it's very useful for a change agent to be able to identify which category definite individuals belong to, since the short-term goal of most modification agents is to assist the adoption of an innovation. Implementation of a new idea is caused by human interface through interpersonal networks. If the initial adopter of an innovation discusses it with two members of a given social system, and these two become adopters who pass the innovation along to two peers, and so on, the resulting distribution follows a binomial expansion. Expect adopter distributions to follow a bell-shaped curve over time (Rogers, 1971)

Adopter Categorization:

The criterion for adopter categorization is innovativeness. This is defined as the degree to which an individual is relatively early in adopting a new idea than other members of a social system. Innovativeness is considered "relative" in that an individual has either more or less of it than others in a social system (Rogers, 1971)

The Mechanism of Diffusion:

Diffusion is the process by which an innovation is communicated through certain channels over time among the members of a social system.

1. Knowledge – person becomes aware of an innovation and has some idea of how it functions.
2. Persuasion – person forms a favorable or unfavorable attitude toward the innovation.
3. Decision – person engages in activities that lead to a choice to adopt or reject the innovation.
4. Implementation – person puts an innovation into use.
5. Confirmation – person evaluates the results of an innovation-decision already made.

Innovation and Entrepreneurship

Practice and Principles

By Peter F. Drucker

Drucker focuses on large-scale entrepreneurship, e.g., aiming to control an industry niche or whole industry, rather than small business management. Drucker discusses innovation, which Drucker says is both conceptual and perceptual. Perceptual in that you must go out and talk with your market to learn from it. Drucker's regular theme is that good entrepreneurship is usually market-focused and market-driven.

Opposing to the belief of many, Drucker says that innovation isn't inspired by a bright idea, rather it "is organized, systematic, sensible work." Innovation can be learned and integrated into a company or non-profit organization.

Drucker gives us guidelines for identifying innovative opportunity. For example, unexpected successes or unexpected failures within an industry often point to opportunity. Drucker also suggests that innovative opportunity exists where there is "an internal strangeness within the pulse or the logic of a process" or a process need.

As a great example, Drucker tells us the story of William Conner, a salesman to the medical industry who decided he wanted to start his own company. Conner went out and spoke with surgeons about the problems and difficulties the surgeons faced.

While talking with surgeons, Conner learned that the process for cataract surgery was generally routine and easy, except there was one incongruity making the surgery difficult and unpleasant for physicians. During the surgery, surgeons had to cut one ligament which involved some risk.

With research Conner learned that there was an enzyme that dissolved this ligament. Conner also learned that new methods of storage could preserve this enzyme allowing it to be used in surgery. After patenting his compound, Conner quickly captured a niche market providing his compound to surgeons performing cataract surgery. No longer did they need to cut the ligament. They could dissolve it. With process need, the market already exists for the innovation. Drucker notes this is a relatively low-risk type of entrepreneurship.

While process need is a great area of entrepreneurial innovation, Drucker also suggests demographics may provide opportunities. I'm more dubious of this. Even though we may know how the population will change in ten years, capitalizing on this change isn't easy. Further, most entrepreneurs already tend to be focused on a particular industry or market and large-scale demographic changes wouldn't induce them to change their company's focus. Plus, there are entrepreneurial opportunities even in declining industries.

Entrepreneurship is risky because so few of the so-called entrepreneurs know what they are doing." This is the basic thesis on page twenty nine of Peter Drucker's seminal book, Innovation and

Entrepreneurship, now over twenty years old. No business-oriented book written since is more relevant or useful to those seeking to understand the next great entrepreneurial opportunity.

Like the discipline of management which he helped found, Drucker believes that innovation can be undertaken in a systematic way and, when it is, the results are consistently positive. He suggests a number of sources that are "low risk" but are often overlooked by aspiring entrepreneurs. Among them are the following:

Demographics:

Changes in demographics are unambiguous, according to Drucker, and they have the most predictable consequences (p.88). There is no better example of this opportunity than the aging of the baby boomers. This cohort represents eighty-two million people in the United States with over one trillion dollars in buying power. As they get older, boomers require more medical services, and their expectations in terms of personal attention and rapid response are legendary. A high percentage of them conduct much of their daily life via e-mail.

Process Need:

Innovation based on a process need starts out with the job to be done. According to Drucker, the need "perfects a process that already exists, replaces a link that is weak, or redesigns an existing old process by supplying the 'missing link' everybody in the organization always knows the need exists. Yet usually no one does anything about it" (p. 69). RichFx, based in New York City, identified such an opportunity as a matter of survival after the Internet bubble burst. The company began as a "bright idea" employing cutting edge computer technology to create three-dimensional online shopping environments. Its pilot sites were aesthetically superb illustrating use of new technology in ways that its potential customers had never envisioned.

Changes in Perception

"If general perception changes from seeing the glass as 'half full' to seeing it as 'half empty' there are major innovative opportunities," writes Drucker (p. 99). A good example is the rise of the micro-breweries. Twenty-five years ago it appeared that obtaining huge scale was the only way to survive in the beer business as the industry underwent massive consolidation. Although this made perfect sense as a means of reducing costs, the beer consumer apparently had a different view. This change in perception was identified by pioneers such as Jim Koch, the founder of the (Samuel Adams) brewery and, in what seemed to be an instant, hundreds of micro-breweries sprung up all over the country. Today, there are 1,368 different breweries in the United States.

Transformational Leadership (theory)

The original formulation of transformational leadership theory comes from Burns (1978). At the core of transformational leadership is the concept of transformation, or change of the organization. (Devanna, 1986a) noted that companies were being asked to make fundamental changes. Transformational leadership best reflects this change (Bass, 1985). (Burns, 1987) Defined transformational leadership as a process in which "leaders and followers raise one another to higher levels of morality and motivation" (p. 20). A chief element of transformation is the ability to cultivate the needs of the follower in a follower centered (person-centered) manner. According to Burns, focusing on needs makes leaders accountable to the follower. First, Burns contended that followers are driven by a moral need, the need to champion a cause, or the need to take a higher moral stance on an issue. People like to feel that a higher organizational spiritual mission guides their motives. The second need is a paradoxical drive for consistency and conflict. Transforming leaders must help followers make sense out of inconsistency. Conflict is necessary to create alternatives and to make change possible. The process of transformation is empathy, understanding, insight, and consideration; not manipulation, power wielding, or coercion. Tichy and Devanna (1986a) defined transformation best, "Transformational leadership is about change, innovation, and entrepreneurship".

Transformational leadership is a process of micro-level and macro-level influence (Yukl, 1989). **At the macro-level**, transformational leaders must take charge of the social systems and reform the

organization by creating an appropriate power situation. At the **micro-level**, transformational leaders must attend to the personalities in the organization to facilitate change at an interpersonal level.

Methodology

Topic:

Impact of innovation in service's organizations (marketing agencies)

4.2: Operational Definitions:

Following are the operational definitions in our research paper:

4.2.1: innovation

An innovation can be defined as simply a better way of doing things or an improvement to an existing product or invention.

4.2.2: Invention:

Invention can be thought of as a new manmade device or process. An example of invention is the internal combustion engine invented in the 1800's.

4.2.2.1: Services

It is often useful to think of services as either intermediation activities, such as transport, that arise because consumers want to separate production and consumption, or contact services, such as haircuts or medical services, where production involves the consumer directly and where the output of the activity is embodied in the consumeran important aspect of a service is the 'jointers' of production and consumption – i.e. that goods can be produced meaningfully without consumers (think of a firm producing a car), whereas services require jointness (a haircut, or **repairing a car**).

4.2.2.2: Economic Performance:

In this article Luisa Ferreira described the relationship between innovation and economic performance, in the services sector, using new data on innovation in service industries. Instead of establishing a simple direct link between innovation and labor productivity, they have taken into account not only the result of the innovation process but also the activities earlier to the market introduction of the innovation. Their work indicates that this may be a relevant determinant of productivity.

4.2.3: Discovery:

Discovery is the primary process used in science to uncover new knowledge. Thomas Edison invented over 1000 patents, but only made one scientific discovery. This discovery was called the "Edison Effect."

4.3. Impact:

It is recognized that some service firms are very prominent actors in technological 'systems of innovation'. Notable amongst these are the 'science based and specialist suppliers. These firms, which include R&D, design and engineering consultancies, frequently spend far more on innovation than typical manufacturers and often have very close links with the science base, in part acting as conduits through which technological knowledge is disseminated throughout the economy.

We can say innovation in making ads bring dramatically changes in the growth of an organization when we asked question from audience attractive ads may increase the sales of an organization 42.5% strongly agree for saying attractive ads increases sale 42.5% was agree and 10% neutral and 5% disagree in the lie this survey we can say attractive ads increases sales.

We can also check the impact and importance of innovation from the result of the question "is there any need of improvement in services"?

77% people are agree 12.5% neutral and 10% were disagree when we asked from them is there any space for improvement in marketing agencies it mean innovation is necessary for business.

4.4. Dependent and Independent Variables Model:

We have a model of dependent and independent variables. **Dependent variables** are sales, employee productivity, employee retention, profits, financial health, performances and Goodwill. **Independent variables** are innovation, R&D.

Table 4.1

Gender				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
male	23	57.5	57.5	57.5
female	17	42.5	42.5	100.0
Total	40	100.0	100.0	

We have done the survey for checking the impact of innovation in marketing agencies. In this survey total no. of persons was 40. From those 40 people 23 were male and 17 were female.

Table 4.2

Age				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
30-40	3	7.5	7.5	7.5
25-30	11	27.5	27.5	35.0
20-25	26	65.0	65.0	100.0
Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation

The age group of 8% was 30-40,
 11% 25-30
 65% 20-25

Table 4.3

Avail services of marketing agency				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
strongly agree	11	27.5	27.5	27.5
Agree	14	35.0	35.0	62.5
Neutral	10	25.0	25.0	87.5
Disagree	4	10.0	10.0	97.5
strongly disagree	1	2.5	2.5	100.0
Total	40	100.0	100.0	

When we asked question have you ever been avail the services of marketing agencies 62% were agree and 38% were disagree.

Table 4.4

marketing necessary				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
strongly agree	20	50.0	50.0	50.0
agree	17	42.5	42.5	92.5
Neutral	2	5.0	5.0	97.5
disagree	1	2.5	2.5	100.0
Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation:

50% strongly agree 42.5 agree and 5 neutral and 2.5 disagree for saying marketing is necessary for business.

Table 4.5

ads increase sale

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
strongly agree	17	42.5	42.5	42.5
agree	17	42.5	42.5	85.0
neutral	4	10.0	10.0	95.0
disagree	2	5.0	5.0	100.0
Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation:

42.5% strongly agree for saying attractive ads increases sale 42.5% was agree and 10% neutral and 5% disagree in the lie this survey we can say attractive ads increases sales.

Table 4.6

social media strong

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
strongly agree	18	45.0	45.0	45.0
agree	15	37.5	37.5	82.5
neutral	6	15.0	15.0	97.5
disagree	1	2.5	2.5	100.0
Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Social media is a strong tool for advertisement because 45% are strongly agree and 38% of population are agree and small portion of total population was disagree.

Table 4.7

online advertisement

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
strongly agree	6	15.0	15.0	15.0
agree	12	30.0	30.0	45.0
neutral	10	25.0	25.0	70.0
disagree	12	30.0	30.0	100.0
Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Online advertisement is costly or not we can say about this because 45% are agree 25% are neutral and 30% were disagree.

Table 4.8

marketing works region

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
strongly agree	7	17.5	17.5	17.5
agree	17	42.5	42.5	60.0
neutral	8	20.0	20.0	80.0
disagree	7	17.5	17.5	97.5
strongly disagree	1	2.5	2.5	100.0
Total	40	100.0	100.0	

60% people says online marketing worker in our region are neutral and 20% disagree from this statement so we can conclude online marketing work in our region.

Table 4.9

difficult to understand

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
strongly agree	1	2.5	2.5	2.5
Agree	10	25.0	25.0	27.5
Neutral	16	40.0	40.0	67.5
disagree	11	27.5	27.5	95.0
strongly Disagree	2	5.0	5.0	100.0
Total	40	100.0	100.0	

28% says it's difficult to understand innovation in marketing agencies 40% are neutral 32% says yes it's difficult to understand the region behind it is unawareness

Table 4.10

Customer innovating

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
strongly agree	6	15.0	15.0	15.0
Agree	11	27.5	27.5	42.5
Neutral	13	32.5	32.5	75.0
disagree	9	22.5	22.5	97.5
5.00	1	2.5	2.5	100.0
Total	40	100.0	100.0	

45% people want to be a part of an innovation where as 30% are neutral and 25% are not agree but it doesn't mean we should not do innovation because we can do it for 25% people who are agree and neutral.

Table 4.11

customer resist innovation

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
strongly agree	5	12.5	12.5	12.5
agree	8	20.0	20.0	32.5
neutral	16	40.0	40.0	72.5
disagree	10	25.0	25.0	97.5
5.00	1	2.5	2.5	100.0
Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation:

Are customer resist innovation? According to our survey result 32% of population said yes while other want to see it

Table 4.12

Q10

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
strongly agree	4	10.0	10.0	10.0
agree	20	50.0	50.0	60.0
neutral	7	17.5	17.5	77.5
disagree	9	22.5	22.5	100.0
Total	40	100.0	100.0	

In this region marketing agencies are operating properly 60% are agree 18% are neutral and rest of these are disagree.

Table 4.13

services are important

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
strongly agree	9	22.5	22.5	22.5
agree	26	65.0	65.0	87.5
neutral	3	7.5	7.5	95.0
disagree	1	2.5	2.5	97.5
5.00	1	2.5	2.5	100.0
Total	40	100.0	100.0	

After sale services are most important for long life of any business 85% of population agree from this statement 7.5% are neutral and just 5% are disagree from this.

Table 4.14

company bear marketing expenses

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
strongly agree	10	25.0	25.0	25.0
Agree	19	47.5	47.5	72.5
Neutral	10	25.0	25.0	97.5
strongly disagree	1	2.5	2.5	100.0
Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation:

70% people says company should bear marketing cost 25% are neutral while 5% disagree.

Table 4.15

enough marketing

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
strongly agree	3	7.5	7.5	7.5
agree	18	45.0	45.0	52.5
neutral	10	25.0	25.0	77.5
disagree	9	22.5	22.5	100.0
Total	40	100.0	100.0	

There is space for introducing new marketing agencies in this region because 52% people says marketing agencies are working properly while others are disagree from this.

Table 4.16

R&D for marketing

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
strongly agree	8	20.0	20.0	20.0
agree	12	30.0	30.0	50.0
neutral	16	40.0	40.0	90.0
disagree	3	7.5	7.5	97.5
strongly disagree	1	2.5	2.5	100.0
Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Companies should do work on R&D 50% are agree, 40% neutral and 10% are disagree.

Table 4.17

change in marketing

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
strongly agree	13	32.5	32.5	32.5
Agree	15	37.5	37.5	70.0
Neutral	5	12.5	12.5	82.5
disagree	6	15.0	15.0	97.5
strongly disagree	1	2.5	2.5	100.0
Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Marketing is charging rapidly its going toward innovation so we can't conclude from our results innovation is much necessary for marketing agencies 70% are agencies 12% neutral and 17% are disagree.

Table 4.18

change consistently

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
strongly agree	9	22.5	22.5	22.5
agree	22	55.0	55.0	77.5
neutral	3	7.5	7.5	85.0
disagree	5	12.5	12.5	97.5
strongly disagree	1	2.5	2.5	100.0
Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Marketing is charging rapidly its going toward innovation so we can't conclude from our results innovation is much necessary for marketing agencies 70% are agencies 12% neutral and 17% are disagree.

Table 4.19

marketing save time

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
strongly agree	10	25.0	25.0	25.0
agree	17	42.5	42.5	67.5
neutral	9	22.5	22.5	90.0
disagree	3	7.5	7.5	97.5
strongly disagree	1	2.5	2.5	100.0
Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Marketing agencies also saves both time and money 67% are agree 22.5%neutral 2.55% disagree.

Table 4.20

improvement services

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
strongly agree	13	32.5	32.5	32.5
agree	18	45.0	45.0	77.5
neutral	5	12.5	12.5	90.0
disagree	3	7.5	7.5	97.5
strongly disagree	1	2.5	2.5	100.0
Total	40	100.0	100.0	

77% people are agree 12.5% neutral and 10% were disagree when we asked from them is there any space for improvement in marketing agencies it mean innovation is necessary for business.

Table 4.21

satisfied with CSR

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
strongly agree	2	5.0	5.0	5.0
agree	21	52.5	52.5	57.5
neutral	8	20.0	20.0	77.5
disagree	8	20.0	20.0	97.5
strongly disagree	1	2.5	2.5	100.0
Total	40	100.0	100.0	

58% complains are going to sought out by customer sales offers 20% are neutral and 22.5% are not going to solution so there huge space for innovation for salving

Table 4.22

company take feedback

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
strongly agree	6	15.0	15.0	15.0
agree	15	37.5	37.5	52.5
neutral	11	27.5	27.5	80.0
disagree	6	15.0	15.0	95.0
strongly disagree	2	5.0	5.0	100.0
Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Company should take feedback from customer to fill up space of innovation 52% people says companies are taking rest of these are disagree from this.

Table 4.23

integrating and attractive advertisement

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
strongly agree	7	17.5	17.5	17.5
agree	21	52.5	52.5	70.0
neutral	9	22.5	22.5	92.5
disagree	1	2.5	2.5	95.0
strongly disagree	2	5.0	5.0	100.0
Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation:

This is an age of innovation with entertainment where we asked question are company’s making entreating adds 70% were agree 22.5% neutral and 7.5% are disagree from this.

6.1 Limitations:

- 1) We have limited time
- 2) Limited number of participant’s
- 3) Border topic difficult to cover
- 4) limited useable things.
- 5) The workroom is limited to tendency in a certain direction in Respondent 1 opinion about the person matter 2 as well as the use of a single work-room square measure and the uncertainty about the generality of discovering after-effects to the use of a single make observations design as well as the use of single work-room other square measure and the generality of discovering after-effects to the use of a single make observations design as well as instruments. For the fact that only NIPOST was used as the part square measure of workroom it is not certain if the same outcome would be get in other organization. Respondent 1 Bias and not A Chillan point of view also make up a greater limiting condition to this make for the fact that form for questions make up the only instrument use to keep (self, thoughts) in order, under control facts and measures-taking make observations design the one and only A designed use for the work-room it is not certain if the same outcome will be used if other sort of

design as well as instrument A were use all these factors make up a greater limiting condition to the make observations.

- 6) Wages are not linked to the level of productivity and Wages guarantee the income for the worker but do not offer a financial incentive to work harder.

6.2 Recommendations:

Following are the recommendations that the companies must be needed.

1. Suggestion from employees:

Organizations should take suggestions from employees because everyone thinks differently and innovation is all about uniqueness and making things easy.

2. Organizations should take feedback from customers:

We can go towards betterment only if we know about our mistakes and the customers are the people who can aware us with our mistakes

3. Attractive adds:

Organizations should make attractive and entertaining ads for getting potential customers

4. Social media

Through our research we find that a social media is a strong tool of marketing and advertisement and it is cheaper than any other tool so companies should work on it appropriately

5. Companies should work on R&D

Research and development is a department who works for innovation and experts interpret future changing's and they introduce new things before competitors through which they became market leader.

6. After sale services

After sales services is a tool through which company can stay in touch with customers so companies should do work on it

6.4 Appendix

Name:

Age:

Gender

Qualification:

QUESTIONNAIRE

No.	Question	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1	Have you ever been avail the services of marketing agencies?					
2	Is marketing necessary for business?					
3	Attractive ads increase sales??					
4	Do you think social media is a strong marketing tool?					
5	Online advertisement is costly?					
6	You think online Marketing works in our region?					
7	Too much difficult to understand?					
8	Customer willing to part of any innovative step?					
9	Customer resist innovation?					
10	Is there marketing agencies properly operating in this region?					
11	DO You think after sale, services are more important?					
12	Do you say companies bear marketing expanses?					
13	Do you think you get enough marketing services for price paid?					
14	Should companies work on R&D for marketing					
15	Do you see any change in marketing in last 2 years?					
16	If yes then is this change consistently coming in every year??					
17	Marketing agencies saves time and money of any business?					
18	Do you think Is there any space of improvement in services?					
19	Are you satisfied with time taken by CSO officer to resolve your complaint?					
20	Company often take feedback from you about their services?					
21	Company often make entertaining and attractive advertisement?					

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